

Molar Conductance, Infra-red, Magnetic Susceptibility, Ultraviolet and Visible Absorption Spectra of Some Amine Complexes of Manganese (II) Chromate

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Co-ordination complexes between manganese (II) chromate and aliphatic amines have been prepared. The structure of the complexes have been resolved on the basis of molar conductance, infra-red, magnetic susceptibility, ultraviolet and visible absorption measurements.

A number of amine complexes of copper (II) and nickel (II) chromate have been prepared and studied^{1,2}. In these complexes chromate ion was found in the outer ionisation sphere. Manganese (II) is reported to form very stable hexamines with a number of inorganic anions. In the present paper, a series of investigations on some amine-compounds of manganese (II) are presented.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Percentages of metal, chromate, carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen indicate the general molecular formula to be $MnCrO_{4.6}$ amine, showing that only six molecules of amines are added, which is also confirmed by the percentage of total bases. Complexes dissolve in nitrobenzene (Conc. of complex $10M^{-3}$) to give conducting solutions and value of molar conductance ranges from 20 to 28 mhos, which is same as for a complex dissociating in two ions³. When a solution of complex is passed through an anionic ion exchange resin, the solution coming down contains only $[Mn(amine)_6]^{2+}$ ion and does not give a precipitate of barium chromate on adding barium acetate. These results suggest that the chromate ion is not co-ordinated to the metal and the formulae of compounds are thus to be written as $[Mn(amine)_6] CrO_4$.

All complexes exhibit a single sharp absorption band in the vicinity of 3250 cm^{-1} , which is assigned to be the NH stretching frequency band. The comparison of position of this band with that of free ammonia (band at 3414 cm^{-1}) and aliphatic amines (band at 3400 cm^{-1}) shows a strong negative shift. The cause of this appears to be the co-ordination of the amine to the metal⁴, which weakens the NH bond and results in the formation of a highly covalent M-N bond. Further, the magnitude of the negative shift of

1. Padmaja Shukla and Gopal Narain, *Current Science* (in press).

2. Gopal Narain, *Z. anorg. allg. chemis* (in press).

3. R. S. Nyholm, *J. Chem. Soc. (London)*, 1957, 1714.

4. K. Nakamoto, "Infra-red Spectra of Inorganic and Co-ordination Compounds" (John Wiley and Sons, New York) 1963, p. 146.

NH stretching frequency decreases as the molecular weight of amine increases, which shows that covalency of the M-N bond and the stability of the complex decreases in the same order. The ammonia complex is thus stablest of all with a shift of about 150 cm.^{-1} while butylamine complex is least stable with a shift of only 60 cm.^{-1} .

The complexes are highly paramagnetic and the value of magnetic moment corresponds to five free spins of electrons. The metal is a d^5 system and in the ground state, each 'd' orbital contains one electron and their spins are parallel. The ground state configuration is thus not being altered by the approach of six ligands, so that the complexes are of high spin type. The ligands use the six octahedral $4s^3 4d^2$ orbitals available now.

The complexes dissolve in formamide and these solutions (after removal of chromate by addition of solid barium acetate, give pale pink solutions) exhibit six to seven absorption bands in the vicinity of 33340, 28570, 27780, 25150, 25060, 23520, and 17860 cm.^{-1} and their molar absorbance values are 0.01, 0.02, 0.022, 0.018, 0.04, 0.015 and 0.018 respectively. The only sextuplet state possible is the 'S' ground state of metal, which is not being split by ligand field. Every conceivable alteration of electron configuration t_{2g}^3 eg.² with all parallel spins, results in the pairing of two or four spins making it a quartet or doublet. Thus all excited states are expected to have different spin multiplicity and transitions to them are spin forbidden. But because of weak spin orbit interactions these transitions are not totally absent but give rise to very weak absorption bands, which is clear by their low molar absorbance values⁵.

Free ion possesses four Russell Saunder's state, which are quartets. The absorption bands can be fitted by taking Δ equal to 8600 cm.^{-1} . The slight shoulder on the sharp band at 25000 cm.^{-1} shows that $4E$ and $4A_1$ states arising from $4G$ are degenerate. The observation of the narrowest bands at 25000 cm.^{-1} and 29500 cm.^{-1} corresponds to the transitions to upper state with zero slope. It is further noted that there are following three states:

$4A_1$	from	$4F$
$4E$	„	$4D$
$4E_1$	„	$4G$
$4A_1$	„	$4G$

and the uppermost band at 25000 cm.^{-1} is due to the transition to the field strength independent $4E_1$, $4A_1$, and hence very narrow.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The compounds were prepared by shaking manganese (II) chromate and amine (1:6 ratio) in 95% ethyl alcohol for three days. The resulting yellowish-brown complex was filtered, washed with alcohol, acetone and dried over P_2O_5 .

1. *Hexamminomanganese (II) chromate*: Found. Mn, 20.08; N, 30.2%. H, 6.31%. CrO_4 , 41.82%, $H_{12}N_6CrO_4$. Mn requires Mn, 20.12%; N, 30.7%; H, 6.59%; CrO_4 , 42.12%.

5. F. A. Cotton and G. Wilkinson, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry" (Interscience Publishers) 1948, p. 701.

2. *Hexamethylaminomanganese (II) chromate*: Found Mn, 15.00%; C, 20.01%; N, 23.21%; H, 8.13%; CrO₄, 32.02%. C₆H₃₀N₆CrO₄. Mn requires Mn, 15.40%; C, 20.20%; N, 23.67%; H, 8.41%; CrO₄, 32.23.

3. *Hexaethylaminomanganese (II) chromate*: Found Mn, 12.20%; C, 32.20%; N, 19.8%; H, 9.20%; CrO₄, 25.7%. C₁₂H₄₂N₆CrO₄. Mn requires Mn, 12.46%; C, 32.66%; N, 19.06%; H, 9.53%; CrO₄, 26.1%.

4. *Hexa-n-propylaminomanganese (II) chromate*: Found Mn, 10.21%; C, 41.0%; N, 15.98%; H, 10.0%; CrO₄, 21.53%. C₁₈H₅₄N₆CrO₄. Mn requires Mn, 10.49%; C, 41.25%; N, 16.04%; H, 10.31%; CrO₄, 21.95%.

5. *Hexa-iso-propylaminomanganese (II) chromate*: Found Mn, 10.39%; C, 40.89%; N, 15.88%; H, 9.9%; CrO₄, 21.4%.

6. *Hexa-n-butylaminomanganese (II) chromate*: Found Mn, 8.98%; C, 45.02%; N, 14.0%; H, 10.89%; CrO₄, 19.18%. C₂₄H₆₆N₆CrO₄. Mn requires Mn, 9.33%; C, 45.51%; N, 14.27%; H, 11.23%; CrO₄, 19.54%.

The infra-red spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer, model 137-B. A sodium chloride prism was used for the complete infra-red region. The KBr disk technique was employed with the solid complexes.

The susceptibilities were obtained by Gouy method at room temperature. The tube was calibrated with A. R. tetraquo. copper (II) sulphate monohydrate.

The ultraviolet and visible absorption spectra were obtained with a Unicam S.P.500 spectrophotometer in formamide (conc. 10⁻³ M).

The data are given in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE I

Percentage of base, molar conductance, infra-red and magnetic susceptibility data

Compound	Percentage of base		Molar conductance (mhos)	NH stretching frequency		μ _{eff} *
	Obs.	Calc.		Band position	negative shift	
1. Hexamminomanganese (II) chromate	37.08	37.42	20.50	3260 cm ⁻¹	154 cm ⁻¹	5.90 B.M.
2. Hexamethylaminomanganese (II) chromate.	52.50	52.10	21.75	3295 cm ⁻¹	115 cm ⁻¹	5.89 B.M.
3. Hexaethylaminomanganese (II) chromate	61.84	61.36	23.80	3288 cm ⁻¹	112 cm ⁻¹	5.88 B.M.
4. Hexa-n-propylaminomanganese (II) chromate	68.00	67.48	20.02	3330 cm ⁻¹	70 cm ⁻¹	5.92 B.M.
5. Hexa-iso-propylaminomanganese (II) chromate	67.98	67.48	24.22	3320 cm ⁻¹	80 cm ⁻¹	5.90 B.M.
6. Hexa-n-butylaminomanganese (II) chromate	71.43	70.90	28.00	3340 cm ⁻¹	60 cm ⁻¹	5.91 B.M.

* Value after the diamagnetic correction had been made.

TABLE 3

Ultraviolet and visible spectral data

Compound	Absorption bands	Molar absorbance
1. Hexamminomanganese (II) chromate	33340, 28370, 27780; 25150, 25010, 23520 and 17850 cm^{-1}	0-01, 0-02, 0-022, 0-018, 0-04, 0-015, 0-018.
2. Hexamethylaminomanganese (II) chromate	33300, 28500, 27780, 21520, 25010, 23520, and 17850 cm^{-1}	0-012, 0-021, 0-022, 0-019, 0-039, 0-018, 0-018
3. Hexaethylaminomanganese (II) chromate	33340, 27780, 25120, 25000, 23520 and 17850 cm^{-1}	0-011, 0-022, 0-02, 0-04, 0-015, 0-019.
4. Hexa-n-propylaminomanganese (II) chromate	33300, 28370, 27700, 25140, 25000 and 17840 cm^{-1}	0-012, 0-022, 0-022, 0-02 0-041, 0-02.
5. Hexa-n-butylaminomanganese (II) chromate	33340, 28370, 27700, 25150, 25000, 23500 and 17850 cm^{-1}	0-012, 0-022, 0-022, 0-019, 0-0415, 0-018, 0-02.

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